

SCARCITY OF SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETERS IN UZBEKISTAN: CAUSES AND POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS*Shakirova A.A.*¹*Abstract:*

The job of a translator has always been ranked as one of the most requested ones. Some industries are inseparable from an interpreting practice, for instance, politics, tourism, or international relationships. The translator's profession has been required since centuries ago: neither negotiations nor governmental meetings can occur without an interpreter. The current-day case has a minor difference with previous times due to the requirement of linguists, who can transfer one's words in an understandable way. In touristical countries like Uzbekistan, the constant development of the translators' profession is a necessity, which is why the government must undertake measures regarding unevolved branches of translation in our country. According to the aforementioned situation, several topics will be discussed in this research article: a) definition of a synchronous translation; b) causes of issue in Uzbekistan; c) probable ways of solution.

Key words: oral translation, simultaneous interpreting, tourism, education system.

Simultaneous interpreter as a multitasking

The appearance of this specialization dates back to 1920, when the businessman Edward Filene's suggestion to replace the consecutive translation with a synchronous one ignited the new branch of interpreting methods. Synchronous interpretation is also a time-managing method of translation, which supplied an opportunity to save time during the conferences, meetings, or summits (Shiryayev, 1979). An oral interpretation is considered to be the most complicated type of translation, especially simultaneous interpreting, since it requires not only professionalism but also stress resistance. Herbert (1952) comprehends it as a three-component process including understanding, conversion, and expression. Due to the large tension of brain cells, simultaneous translators have to make breaks every 20 minutes of their work, during which it is advised to regain lost energy by eating chocolate or nuts. Moreover, a specialist who takes the responsibility of a translator ought to be acknowledged in cultural, historical, and geographical aspects of the countries whose languages are involved in the translation process (Malikova, 2020). Therefore, the theory that the interpreter should be wide-minded and intelligent in variable spheres reveals the long educational path that must be passed before achieving professionalism. The segment of complexity of this job is also believed to be an obstacle for youth on the way to enrollment, particularly for these courses. Nevertheless, there are both advantages and drawbacks in the job of simultaneous translator, as in any other one.

The current condition of synchronous interpretation in Uzbekistan is not awful but requires a higher level for such a kind of touristic country. Since Uzbekistan is not solely concentrated in mass tourism but also in congress and business tourism, MICE (Meetings, Incentives, Conferences, and Exhibitions) tourism and various exchange programs, transliterators specializing in technical translation, juridical, economic, and medical translation are required.

Roots of an issue with the lack of synchronous translators in Uzbekistan

Above all, the absence of a bachelor's degree in this specialty represents the basis of the problem, which is why some of the really talented teenagers are not able to reveal and evolve their skills. Furthermore, some parts of society are even uninformed about the existence of this type of job. Existing professionals in this field gained their knowledge abroad or through self-studying, which demonstrates that there are indeed few educational institutions of this branch in our country. The circumstances seem to be not so unpleasant; however, the performance of self-taught employees in this sphere is full of misinterpretations, which results in unproductivity and poor quality of interpreting service in Uzbekistan. Whereas, sometimes even for well-educated interpreters, it is possible to make errors because of strong worrying and stress.

Another considerable barrier is poor supply of technical equipment. The lack of necessary technic leads to the prevention of effective accomplishment of the work, let alone practice activity for students. Proceeding to a practice spectrum, there are minor opportunities for students or professionals who want to evolve their skills to have a practical experience. Since the development of proficiency occurs through the efforts and

¹ *Shakirova Anastasiya Abduvasiyevna, 1-year student of "Silk Road" International University of Tourism and Cultural Heritage Department of translation and interpreting studies*

struggles during the process, which is called practicing, workers of this specialty have no access to it due to the absence of facilities.

The high requirements of the profession also play a role in the sparsity of workers as an interpreter. The representatives of this specialty need the constant evolution of their proficiency due to the continual transformation of the structure and vocabulary of languages. On this basis, they always have to visit various seminars or courses in order to be informed of any linguistic changes. The information mentioned above illustrates a high level of stress on account of strong concentration during the process. According to the scientific report, the pulse of a simultaneous interpreter while doing the job is 160 per minute, which is incredibly fast. Moreover, the synchronous interpreter has no time in reserve; that means the answer must be supplied 2 times faster than during the consecutive translation and 20-30 times faster than during a written one.

Probable resolutions of the inconvenience regarded simultaneous interpreters in Uzbekistan

There are a number of measures for the improvement of the current situation. Plan "A": there is an option of providing linguists with courses abroad, after which the second step is to organize the faculty or department of simultaneous interpretation, where already educated specialists will be able to distribute their gained knowledge. Plan "B" is directed to the invitation of foreign professional interpreters to nurture a new generation of this department, who will be the source of knowledge in the future. An additional piece of advice is to create interpreters' communities, whose responsibilities will include the organization of educational courses, seminars, lectures, and other events. The prestige of the job should be increased as well by wage-lifting and informing society about the necessity and demand of this specialty. The problem regarding the technical sector must be eliminated also through dealing with large, influential companies that are able to equip the country with special devices or make a collaborative union to give an opportunity for the country to construct necessary equipment by itself.

Conclusion

The importance of the occupation of translator, either oral or written, is substantial in Uzbekistan. Consequently, this specialization must undoubtedly be improved by several effective methods mentioned above by eliminating all the defects such as equipment flaws, lack of teaching professionals, and awareness about the existence and benefit of this job. Despite the difficulty of the interpreter's practice and study process, the youth generation should be well-acknowledged about both edges of this industry in order to understand, whether they are interested in the career of interpreter or not. Approximately 4 years should be allocated for the implementation of this project. After all the procedures are done, the situation in the country will contrast with the previous one.

The importance of the occupation of translator, either oral or written, is substantial in Uzbekistan. Consequently, this specialization must undoubtedly be improved by several effective methods mentioned above by eliminating all the defects such as equipment flaws, lack of teaching professionals, and awareness about the existence and benefit of this job. Despite the difficulty of the interpreter's practice and study process, the youth generation should be well-acknowledged about both edges of this industry in order to understand, whether they are interested in the career of interpreter or not. Approximately 4 years should be allocated for the implementation of this project. After all the procedures are done, the situation in the country will contrast with the previous on

References:

- [1]. Kilian G. Seeber. (2015). *Simultaneous interpreting*. University of Geneva.
- [2]. Malikova A. A. (2020). *Role of conference interpreter in the field of international relations*. Research article. Pskov State University, Pskov, Russia.
- [3]. Комиссаров В.Н. (1990). *Теория перевода*. Издательство «Высшая школа», 101430, Москва, ГСП-4, Неглинная ул., д. 29/14.
- [4]. Ширяев А. Ф. (1979). *Синхронный перевод*. Военное издательство министерства обороны СССР